

Sum of Series involving Anna Iota Function and Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: This paper discusses how the series involving the Riemann zeta function relates to the series involving the Annamalai iota function. The Riemann zeta function is the most important special functions that that plays a vital role in the area of analytic number theory and has applications in applied statistics, physics, and probability theory.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as an important role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the Riemann zeta function [17-19]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [20].

2. Relation between Riemann Zeta Function and Annamalai Iota Function

The Riemann zeta function for all complex numbers is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots$$

This zeta function $\zeta(s)$ converges for all complex numbers s and $Re(s) > 1$.

The Annamalai iota function $l(s)$ for all complex numbers is defined by

$$l(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s} = -1 + \frac{1}{2^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} - \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} = \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots$$

This iota function $l(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $Re(s) > 0$.

Theorem 2.1: $\zeta(s) = 2^{s-1}[\zeta(s) + l(s)]$, $Re(s) > 1$.

Proof. Let prove this theorem as follows:

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} - \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \frac{2}{2^s} + \frac{2}{4} + \frac{2}{6^s} + \frac{2}{8^s} + \frac{2}{10^s} + \frac{2}{12^s} + \frac{2}{14^s} + \frac{2}{16^s} + \frac{2}{18^s} + \frac{2}{20^s} + \frac{2}{22^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \frac{2}{(2 \times 1)^s} + \frac{2}{(2 \times 2)^s} + \frac{2}{(2 \times 3)^s} + \frac{2}{(2 \times 4)^s} + \frac{2}{(2 \times 5)^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \frac{2}{2^s \times 1^s} + \frac{2}{2^s \times 2^s} + \frac{2}{2^s \times 3^s} + \frac{2}{2^s \times 4^s} + \frac{2}{2^s \times 5^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \frac{1}{2^{s-1} \times 1^s} + \frac{1}{2^{s-1} \times 2^s} + \frac{1}{2^{s-1} \times 3^s} + \frac{1}{2^{s-1} \times 4^s} + \frac{1}{2^{s-1} \times 5^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) + l(s) = \frac{1}{2^{s-1}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{10^s} + \dots \right)$$

From this sum of series mentioned above, we get

$$\zeta(s) = 2^{s-1}[\zeta(s) + l(s)], \quad \text{Re}(s) > 1.$$

Hence proved.

Example: $\zeta(2) + l(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{24}$.

Let us prove this equation shown in the example.

The Basel problem [21] indicates that $\zeta(2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$.

$$\zeta(2) + l(2) = \frac{1}{2^2} \zeta(2) = \frac{1}{2^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}.$$

Here, $\frac{1}{2^2} \zeta(2) = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{6} \right) = \frac{\pi^2}{24}$.

$$\therefore \zeta(2) + l(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{24}.$$

Hence proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the author has shown the relationship between the Annamalai iota function and the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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